

REINFORCING AND COMPATIBILIZING EFFECT OF NANO SIZE MONTMORILLONITE ON HIGH DENSITY POLYETHYLENE - POLYAMIDE 6 COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Polymer blending is a widely applied method in the industry to tailor materials for specific applications. It has relatively low cost compared to developing a new polymer [1]. By mixing two or more polymers their properties can be combined, and by changing the components and their composition the properties of the system can be varied in a wide range [2, 3]. Significant numbers of polymer blends are immiscible, and thus a phase separation occurs after melt mixing step at room temperature [4, 5]. Blend properties are highly influenced by the blend morphology and the chemical interaction on the interfaces.

In the last few years beside the traditionally used chemical coupling agents, the effect of nano sized particles as compatibilizers are more and more widely studied in polymer blends [6]. Nanoparticles have a strong effect on the microstructure of the immiscible polymer blends; they resulted in the decrease of the minor phase and thus finer microstructure [7-9].

The positive effect of using nanostructured materials in polymer matrix have been reported in many papers. By using clay minerals like montmorillonite the gas permeability and the heat resistance of the composite can be decreased due to the Barrier-effect and the mechanical properties can be increased.

The key of the effectiveness of clay reinforced nanocomposites is exfoliating the mineral and dispersing it uniformly in the polymer matrix. The nanocomposite properties depend on the size and the surface properties of the reinforcement.

There are several methods for modify the montmorillonite layers to achieve compatibility with

the polymer matrix: by exchange with alkylammonium ions or by using different compatibilizers in the melt mixing step.

Recently, high-energy ball milling has been recognized as an efficient method for particle size reduction, structural changes and the optimization of the powder properties [10].

In the last decade several investigations focused on the structural modification of the clay minerals by high energy ball milling [11-16]. Frost et al. found that the degree of intercalation decreased by increasing the milling time in case of kaolinit [17] or in another study the aggregation of the clay particles was observed [18].

Xia et al. found that after wet grinding, the d_{001} spacing of purified montmorillonite increased from 1.22 to 1.52 nm, when the ratio of the weight of the balls to the powder was 40:1. The time of grinding varied from 1 to 4 h. The best properties, including better space and ability of attracting cations of interlayers, and less defects was observed after 1 hour grinding [19].

Ramadan et al. investigated the effect of ball milling on the structure of montmorillonite and they found an increased structural disorder [20]. It was concluded, that ball milling served as an alternative for exfoliating clay mineral particles.

The ball milling was found also an effective method for preparing nanocomposites by Mangiacapra et al. They applied solid state mixing of pectin and montmorillonite to prepare nanocomposite [21].

In our experiments immiscible polymer blends composed of HDPE and PA6 were produced, montmorillonite and chemical coupling agent were added in different amounts. To achieve better

homogenization and intercalation of the montmorillonite (MMT) nanolayers mechanical milling of MMT was applied prior to the compounding. The effect of compatibilizer, nanoclay and the milling time were studied on the mechanical properties and the microstructure of the blends were analysed.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

All the materials used in this study are commercially available. High-density polyethylene (HDPE, TIPELIN 6000B (TVK, Hungary), MFR: 1.30 g/10 min (5 kg, 190 °C), and polyamide 6 (PA6, HVF (A. Schulman)) were blended as matrix materials.

Chemical coupling agent (Polybond 3009 (Chemtura Corp.) – PEGMA (Mw=186000)) was added in 1wt% (related to the matrix weight) – to the polymer blends.

As nano reinforcement layered structure montmorillonite (MMT, Cloisite 20 A, Southern Clay Products) was applied in 1wt% and 3wt% (Fig.1.). Cloisite 20A is a natural montmorillonite that has been ion exchanged with dimethyl, dehydrogenated tallow, and quaternary ammonium chloride to form an organoclay.

Fig.1. TEM micrograph of the montmorillonite structure.

2.2 Sample preparation

Sample preparation was a two-step process, proposed from compounding and test specimen preparation with different production technologies.

Compounding and test specimen production

Polymers (75% HDPE and 25% PA6) were compounded (blended) in a LabTech Scientific-type laboratory twin-screw extruder (Fig.2.).

The zone temperatures of the extrusion were 180 to 240°C.

Fig.2. Laboratory twin-screw extruder used for our experiments.

In the melt mixing step PEGMA (1%) and MMT (1% and 3%) were incorporated separately or in a combination of 1% PEGMA and 1% or 3% MMT. Amounts of PEGMA and MMT are related to the common weight of HDPE and PA6 polymers.

All blends were injection moulded at 240 °C to produce standard specimens for the tests of mechanical properties.

The raw materials were dried before the extrusion and the injection moulding at least 16 hours on 80°C.

Attrition milling

Mechanical milling of MMT was carried out prior to the melt mixing step by an attritor (Union Process, type 01-HD/HDDM).

The powder like nanoclay were introduced in a 1400 cm³ stainless steel vessel together with stainless steel balls (3/16" in diameter) and were dry milled in three different intervals (10 min, 30 min and 120

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min). Rotation speed was 420 rpm and the ball-to-powder mass ratio was 30 to 1.

The UP-HD/HDDM-01 type attritor used for the milling experiments of the montmorillonite and its schematic picture can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig.3. UP-HD/HDDM-01 type attritor and its schematic picture used for the milling experiments of the montmorillonite.

2.3 Testing methods

The specimens used for three point bending and the impact tests were made by cutting the ends of the dump-bell shaped samples. All specimens were conditioned (50% RH, 23°C) at least 24 hours before testing.

The composition and the identification of tested materials are summarized in the following table (Table 1). The weight percentage of the additives was related to the matrix mass. The ratio of the

matrix materials: HDPE and PA6 was 75/25 for each composition.

Composition	MMT [wt%]	PEgMA [wt%]	Milling Time [min]
Blend	0	0	-
1M	1	0	0
3M	3	0	0
1K_1M	1	1	0
1K_3M	3	1	0
1K_3M(1)	3	1	10
1K_3M(2)	3	1	30
1K_3M(3)	3	1	120

Table 1. Composition of the different blends including the milling time data of montmorillonite.

Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature on a standard tensile Instron machine, model 3344 equipped with a 2 kN load cell (cross-head speed of 1 mm/min and then 50 mm/min).

Three point bending tests were performed by Instron 5582 equipment (support span of 6.4 mm, loading speed of 2 mm/min).

Charpy impact tests were carried out as per ISO 179-1 standard by using a 15 J pendulum impact machine (Model 8545/000, CEAST) at room temperature on single-notched specimens.

The melt volume rates (MVR) of all formulations were measured by a CEAST 7026 Modular Melt Flow Index tester at 240°C and by 10 kg load.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed using SETARAM DSC131 equipment. In order to erase any thermal history effect, the samples were heated from 30°C to 270°C, cooled to 30°C, and then they were heated again up to 270°C. The data presented refer to the second heating scans. The heating and cooling cycles were all carried out at 20 °C min⁻¹. The crystallization (T_c) and melting (T_m) temperatures were determined by cooling and heating thermograms, respectively.

The morphology of the blends was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were fractured cryogenically (in liquid nitrogen) and then covered with gold. Then the fractured samples were observed in a SEM instrument at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV.

3 Results and discussion

In all cases the neat blend served as reference material without any additive.

Tensile properties

As it clearly seen on Fig. 4, chemical compatibilizer has a measurable effect on the tensile strength. 12 % increase was found and further improvement by about 9 % could be achieved by the mechanical milling of MMT. The tensile strength decreased by increasing the milling time, presumably because of the agglomeration of the MMT particles.

Fig.4. Tensile strength of neat and modified/nanocomposite 75HDPE/25PA6 based polymer blends (K: PEgMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

The same tendency of milling time was occurred in case of Young's modulus; while in this characteristic the montmorillonite has the major rule. 20% improvement can be achieved and at higher MMT content by applying 10 min of attrition milling, much higher: 26% improvement was found (Fig.5).

Fig.5. Young's modulus of blends (K: PEgMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

Bending properties

Stronger effect of the nanoclay was found in case of bending properties. Flexural strength and modulus increased by ~ 20% by using 3%MMT, and further 18% or 12% improvements were found in flexural strength and modulus respectively by the mechanical treatment of the montmorillonite (Fig.6-7).

Fig.6. Flexural strength of neat and modified/nanocomposite 75HDPE/25PA6 based polymer blends (K: PEgMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

By increasing the milling time, both the flexural strength and modulus decreased as earlier in case of tensile properties.

Fig.7. Flexural modulus of neat and modified/nanocomposite 75HDPE/25PA6 based polymer blends (K: PEgMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

Impact behaviour

As it is well-known in the scientific literature there is an opposite relationship between the stiffness and the toughness: the highest is the modulus the lowest is the stiffness. The results of the Charpy impact

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tests are in accordance with this tendency (Fig. 8). The impact strength of most blend compositions decreased.

Fig.8. Results of Charpy impact tests (K: PEGMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

Flowing characteristic

To characterize the processability of the blends melt flow test was carried out and the melt volume rates (MVR) [cm³/10 min] were determined. The results for the different blends are presented in Fig.9.

Fig.9. Results of melt flow tests of neat and modified/nanocomposite 75HDPE/25PA6 based polymer blends (K: PEGMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

The MVR value improved by adding 1 wt% MMT to the blend, and decreased dramatically by applying chemical compatibilizer. Attrition milling seemed to be having a slight (positive) effect on this characteristic.

DSC measurements

The DSC traces of the second heating scans for the different samples are shown in Fig. 10, and the temperatures, T_m , and the enthalpies, ΔH_m , of the melting peaks are summarized below in Table 2.

Sample	HDPE		PA6	
	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)
HDPE/PA6	136.5	94.3	221.7	13.8
1M	136.7	123.5	214.4	5.9
3M	144.2	102.0	218.0	11.3
1K_1M*	137.4	116.2	214.8	7.3
1K_3M	142.0	103.0	216.9	8.5
1 K_3 M(1)	140.0	114.7	215.9	8.4
1 K_3 M(2)	136.9	115.7	215.0	10.0
1 K_3 M(3)	135.8	101.3	215.1	9.1

*: 1 wt% PEGMA (K) and 1 wt% MMT (M) in HDPE/PA6 (75/25wt%) blend

Table 2. Temperatures, T_m , and enthalpies, ΔH_m , of the melting peaks of the second DSC heating scans for various samples.

Fig.10. DSC traces of the second heating scans of neat and modified/nanocomposite 75HDPE/25PA6 based polymer blends (K: PEGMA, M: montmorillonite, milling time: (1)-10 min, (3)-30 min, (3)-120 min).

The PEGMA and the nanoclay affected the melting temperatures of both polymer components. The melting point of PA6 in the blend decreased in all case, the best result was found at 3% MMT content.

In case of high density polyethylene the chemical coupling agent has positive effect on the melting temperature, but stronger effect could be found by adding 3wt% MMT alone. The higher melting temperature of the HDPE phase denotes better heat resistance.

Mechanical milling had negative effect on the melting temperature. Applying higher milling time

the same or lower values was found for the melting temperature of HDPE phase, and lower melting points were measured in case of PA6.

Blend Morphology

Fig.11. shows the typical morphology of the incompatible HDPE/PA6 blend, in which a dispersed droplet morphology and smooth interface can be observed.

In comparison to neat PA6/HDPE blend (Fig. 11(a)), the size of dispersed phase decreases significantly by adding PEGMA and MMT (Fig. 11(b)).

a

b

Fig. 11. SEM micrographs of pure and nanocomposite blends (a) HDPE / PA6 75/25; (b) HDPE/PA6 with 1% PEGMA and 3% MMT.

4 Conclusion

Blends of PA6 and HDPE (25/75 wt%) were produced by melt mixing in a laboratory twin screw extruder. The effect of PEGMA as chemical coupling agent and montmorillonite used in different ratios were examined on the processability, thermal and the mechanical properties of the blends. Their morphologies were also analysed. In this study the MMT were dry milled by attritor before the compounding and the influence of the milling time was also investigated.

As a conclusion, it can be stated that applying MMT alone or together with PEGMA has a measurable positive effect on the static mechanical properties (18-20% in case of tensile and bending modulus).

Attrition milling of the montmorillonite prior compounding has a influenced mainly the static mechanical properties. These characteristics, strength and modulus showed further improvement, by 8-16% in tensile and 12-18% in bending properties.

By increasing the milling time the above mentioned these mechanical parameters decreased presumably caused by the agglomeration of the MMT particles.

The impact strength and the flowability decreased in all cases.

Montmorillonite in the blend increased the melting point of the polyethylene, which is decrease by attrition milling, and further decrease was measured by increasing the milling time.

Montmorillonite and the compatibilizer affected not only the material properties but also the microstructure. Finer structure, lower droplets of the dispersed phase was occurred.

Milling has a great potential to improve the exfoliation and thus the mechanical and other properties of the MMT reinforced polymer composites. Further experiments are need to optimizing the milling parameters and by using liquid nitrogen as milling medium.

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References

- [1] Lan-Peng Li et al. "Characterization of PA6/EPDM-g-MA/HDPE ternary blends: The role of core-shell structure" *Polymer*, Vol. 53, No. 14, pp. 3043–3051, 2012.
- [2] Hargitai H. and Rácz I. "Applications of Macro- and Microfiller-Reinforced Polymer Composites" in *"Polymer Composites: Volume 1"*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, pp. 749-79, 2012.
- [3] Utracki L.A. *"Commercial polymer blends"* Chapman and Hall, London 1998.
- [4] Pernot H, Baumert M, Court F, Leibler L. "Design and properties of co-continuous nanostructured polymers by reactive blending". *Nature Materials*, Vol. 1, pp. 54–58, 2002.
- [5] Filippone G., Dintcheva N.Tz., La Mantia F.P., Acierno D. "Using organoclay to promote morphology refinement and co-continuity in high-density polyethylene/polyamide 6 blends - Effect of filler content and polymer matrix composition." *Polymer*, Vol. 51, pp. 3956-3965, 2010.
- [6] Elias L., Fenouillot F., Majesté JC., Cassagnau P. "Morphology and rheology of immiscible polymer blends filled with silica nanoparticles." *Polymer*, Vol. 48, pp. 6029-6040, 2007.
- [7] Chow WS, Mohd Ishak ZA, Karger-Kocsis J.. "Morphological and Rheological Properties of Polyamide 6 / Poly(propylene) / Organoclay Nanocomposites." *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, Vol. 290., pp. 122-127, 2005.
- [8] Lee MH, Dan CH, Kim JH, Cha J, Kim S, Hwang Y, Lee CH. "Effect of clay on the morphology and properties of PMMA/poly(styrene-co-acrylonitrile) / clay nanocomposites prepared by melt mixing." *Polymer*, Vol. 47., pp. 4359-4369, 2006.
- [9] Mallick S., Khatua B. B. "Morphology and properties of nylon6 and high density polyethylene blends in absence and presence of nanoclay" *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 121., pp. 359-368, 2011.
- [10] Wei, D., Craig, I.K. "Grinding mill circuits. A survey of control and economic concerns." *International Journal of Mineral Processing*, Vol. 90 (1-4), pp. 56-66, 2009.
- [11] Dellisanti, F; Valdré G. "Study of structural properties of ion treated and mechanically deformed commercial bentonite." *Applied Clay Science / Special Issue*, Vol. 28., No. 1-4., pp. 233-244, 2005.
- [12] F. Dellisanti, V. Minguzzi, G. Valdrè. "Thermal and structural properties of Ca-rich montmorillonite mechanically deformed by compaction and shear." *Applied Clay Science*, Vol. 31., pp. 282–289, 2006.
- [13] Jana Hrachová, Jana Madejová, Peter Billik, Peter Komadel, Vladimír Štefan Fajnor. "Dry grinding of Ca and octadecyltrimethyl ammonium montmorillonite." *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, Vol. 316., No. 2, pp. 589-595, 2007.
- [14] G.E. Christidis, P. Makri, V. Perdikatsis "Influence of grinding on the structure and colour properties of talc, bentonite and calcite white fillers" *Clay Minerals*, Vol. 39., pp. 163–175, 2004.
- [15] Karla Čech Barabaszová, Marta Valášková "Characterization of vermiculite particles after different milling techniques." *Powder Technology*, Vol. 239., pp. 277-283, 2013.
- [16] Neda Vdović, Irena Jurina, Srečo D. Škapin, Ivan Sondi "The surface properties of clay minerals modified by intensive dry milling" *Applied Clay Science*, Vol. 48. No 4., pp. 575-580, 2010.
- [17] R.L. Frost, E. Horvath, E. Mako, J. Kristof, T. Cseh "The effect of mechanochemical activation upon the intercalation of a high-defect kaolinite with formamide" *Journal of Colloid Interface Science*, Vol. 265, pp. 386–395, 2003.
- [18] G. Mani, Q. Fan, S.C. Ugbolue, I.M. EIFF "Size reduction of clay particles in nanometer dimensions" *Materials Research Society Symposium Proceedings*, p. 740, 2003.
- [19] Maosheng Xia, Yinshan Jiang, Lei Zhao, Fangfei Li, Bing Xue, Mengmeng Sun, Darui Liu, Xuguang Zhang "Wet grinding of montmorillonite and its effect on the properties of mesoporous montmorillonite" *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, Vol. 356., No. 1–3., pp. 1-9, 2010.

- [20] Adham R. Ramadan, Amal M.K. Esawi, Ahmed Abdel Gawad "Effect of ball milling on the structure of Na⁺-montmorillonite and organo-montmorillonite (Cloisite 30B)" *Applied Clay Science*, Vol. 47, No. 3-4, pp. 196-202, 2010.
- [21] Pasqualina Mangiacapra, Giuliana Gorrasi, Andrea Sorrentino, Vittoria Vittoria "Biodegradable nanocomposites obtained by ball milling of pectin and montmorillonites" *Carbohydrate Polymers*, Vol. 64., No 4., pp. 516-523, 2006.